

BUILDING A CIVILIZED DIGITAL CIVILIZATION: THE URGENCY OF ISLAMIC VALUES FOR THE YOUNG MUSLIM GENERATION IN THE 5.0 ERA

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Abstract

The advancement of digital technology in the modern era has brought about significant changes in ways of thinking, behaving, and interacting, particularly among the younger generation. The rapid flow of global information is often unfiltered by moral and spiritual values, potentially distancing the younger generation from the true teachings of Islam. In this context, instilling Islamic values is crucial to ensure that the use of digital technology remains within the bounds of Islamic law and good morals. This study aims to outline the concept and strategy for instilling Islamic values in the use of digital media, based on the perspectives of the Qur'an, Hadith, and the thoughts of Islamic scholars. The research method employed a qualitative approach through a literature review of relevant Islamic literature. The study's results indicate that values such as piety, trustworthiness, iffah (maintaining honor), tabligh (conveying the truth), and mas'uliyah (responsibility) must be the foundation of digital ethics for the younger generation. Through Islamic education, parental role models, and the development of a healthy social and virtual environment, these values can be internalized, enabling digital technology to become a means of preaching, education, and strengthening faith. Thus, instilling Islamic values is not only a moral bulwark, but also a direction for the younger generation to utilize digital progress in a civilized, productive manner, and in accordance with Islamic guidance.

Keywords: *Islamic values, young generation, digital ethics, noble character, technology in Islam*

INTRODUCTION

The development of digital technology in the modern era has had a significant impact on all aspects of human life. Today's society is inseparable from technological advances, which offer convenience in various fields such as communication, information, education, and entertainment. The digital world has become a new space for people to interact, express themselves, and acquire knowledge without geographical boundaries. However, behind this progress, serious challenges arise concerning morality and spirituality, especially for the younger generation of Muslims. As the successors of Islamic civilization, the younger generation holds a strategic position in determining the future direction of the community. They are valuable assets who will build a civilization based on Islamic values if equipped with strong faith and morals. However, the reality shows that the rapid flow of globalization and the penetration of digital culture often erode religious values. Many teenagers and young adults are more familiar with online popular culture than with the noble values of the Quran and Sunnah. From an Islamic perspective, technological progress should be a means of strengthening faith and good deeds, not the other way around. Allah SWT says in QS. Al-'Alaq verses 1–5:

اقْرَأْ بِاسْمِ رَبِّكَ الَّذِي خَلَقَ. خَلَقَ الْإِنْسَانَ مِنْ عَلَقٍ. اقْرَأْ وَرَبُّكَ الْأَكْرَمُ. الَّذِي عَلَّمَ بِالْقَلَمِ. عَلَّمَ الْإِنْسَانَ مَا لَمْ يَعْلَمْ

Read it with (mentioning) the name of your Lord who created. He created man from a clot of blood. Read, and your Lord is the Most Gracious, Who teaches (humans) through the medium of kalam. He taught man what he did not know.”

This verse shows that Islam highly values the process of learning and the use of science, including technology, as long as it is used with the right intentions and goals, namely for the benefit and devotion to Allah SWT.

Unfortunately, in modern life, the use of digital technology is often not accompanied by ethical values and responsibility. Phenomena such as the spread of hoaxes, hate speech, negative content, and consumerist behavior on social media demonstrate the weak self-control and appreciation of spiritual values among young users. Yet, the Prophet Muhammad (peace be upon him) warned in his saying:

إِنَّ مِنْ حُسْنِ إِسْلَامِ الْمَرْءِ بَعِيْهِ

Indeed, one of the signs of a person's good Islam is that he leaves behind things that are not beneficial to him."

This hadith emphasizes the importance of ethics in all behavior, including in the digital world. The younger generation of Muslims needs to be guided to be aware of using digital media only for beneficial and worshipful purposes.

Islamic education plays a very strategic role in instilling these values. The primary goal of Islamic education is not only to produce intellectually intelligent individuals, but also to cultivate faithful, noble morals, and the ability to actualize Islamic teachings in real life. Islamic education emphasizes a balance between spiritual, intellectual, emotional, and social aspects, as explained in the words of Allah SWT:

وَابْتَغِ فِيمَا آتَاكَ اللهُ الدَّارَ الْآخِرَةَ وَلَا تَنْسَ نَصِيبَكَ مِنَ الدُّنْيَا

"And seek what Allah has bestowed upon you (happiness) in the land of the afterlife, and do not forget your share of (the pleasures of) this world." (QS. Al-Qashash: 77)

This verse shows the balance in a Muslim's life between the interests of this world and the hereafter. Technology and the digital world are part of worldly affairs which can be a means to goodness in the afterlife if used in the corridor of Islamic values. Islamic education in the digital era must transform not only in its methods but also in the substance of learning. Teachers, lecturers, and parents need to be role models in using technology wisely and with religious values. Internalization of the values of piety, trustworthiness, *effah* (faithfulness), *tabligh* (promise), and *mas'uliyah* (compassionateness) needs to be carried out continuously through habituation, role modeling, and contextual approaches relevant to the digital world. For example, teaching students to be honest in online exams, instilling a sense of responsibility in interactions on social media, and fostering awareness of *tabayyun* (information verification) before spreading news. Instilling Islamic values is not only the responsibility of formal educational institutions, but also of the family and community. Parents have the primary responsibility for providing moral education, as emphasized in the hadith of the Prophet Muhammad (peace be upon him):

كُلُّكُمْ رَاعٍ وَكُلُّكُمْ مَسْئُولٌ عَنْ رَعِيَّتِهِ

*"Each of you is a leader, and each of you will be asked about those you lead."

In the context of the digital world, this hadith can be interpreted as meaning that every Muslim must be responsible for their digital footprint and the content they produce. The younger generation needs to be guided to understand that all activities in cyberspace are recorded by Allah SWT, as stated in His Word:

مَا يَلْفِظُ مِنْ قَوْلٍ إِلَّا لَدَيْهِ رَقِيبٌ عَتِيدٌ

"He uttered not a single word but there was a guardian angel nearby who was always present." (QS. Qaf: 18)

With this awareness, Islamic education can shape a young generation with digital literacy based on faith and morals, so that technology becomes a tool for preaching and strengthening morals, not a source of value decline. Therefore, in this era of increasingly rapid technological advancement, serious and systematic efforts are needed to instill Islamic values in the younger generation. These values must be the primary foundation in every aspect of life, including in the fast-paced and open digital world. Islamic education plays a crucial role in developing spiritual awareness and digital ethics so that young Muslims can become intelligent, moral, and civilized users of technology in accordance with Islamic principles.

METHOD

This research uses a descriptive qualitative approach, focusing on understanding the meaning, values, and process of instilling Islamic values in the use of digital technology by Generation Z in the 5.0 era. This approach was chosen to allow researchers to deeply explore the social and religious realities that occur among young Muslims in their interactions in the digital world. A qualitative approach emphasizes understanding phenomena based on their natural context and the researcher's interpretation of the meanings constructed by the research subjects. Therefore, this study aims not to test hypotheses, but rather to gain a deeper understanding of how Islamic values are instilled, understood, and practiced in the digital world.

This approach also aligns with the character of Islamic education, which emphasizes moral, spiritual, and social values. According to Abuddin Nata, ideally, Islamic education research should not only measure cognitive aspects but also explore the affective dimensions and religious values inherent in students.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The Society 5.0 era is a new phase of civilization that places humans at the center of all digital technology-based activities. In this context, technology is not just a tool, but an integral part of social, economic, educational, and spiritual life. The younger generation of Muslims, as digital natives, live in a space characterized by artificial intelligence, big data, and the internet of things, bringing both convenience and challenges to values and morality. However, reality shows that technological advancement is often not matched by spiritual and moral maturity. Phenomena such as the spread of hoaxes, hate speech, cyberbullying, and indecent content on social media are evidence that digital civilization is not yet fully civilized. Yet, Islam guides its followers to utilize science and technology as a means of benefit, as Allah SWT states in Surah Al-Mujadalah verse 11:

“Allah will exalt those who believe among you and those who are given knowledge, by degrees.”

(QS. Al-Mujadalah: 11)

This verse emphasizes that advances in science and technology should go hand in hand with faith and morals.

a. Islamic Values as the Foundation of Digital Civilization

Islamic values are the primary foundation for building a civilized digital civilization. In Islam, values such as **honesty (şidq)**, **trustworthiness**, **responsibility**, **ethical speech**, and **self-control (taqwa)** are moral principles that must be internalized in digital behavior.

b. Honesty Value (Şidq) :

In digital media, honesty guides the younger generation to spread true and beneficial information. The Prophet Muhammad (peace be upon him) said:

"Be honest, because honesty leads to goodness, and goodness leads to heaven."
(HR. Bukhari and Muslim)

c. Values of Trust and Responsibility :

Every digital activity—whether creating content, managing data, or interacting online—is a form of trust. Allah SWT says:

"Indeed, We have offered a trust to the heavens, the earth and the mountains, so all of them are reluctant to carry that trust and they are afraid they will betray it; and this trust is carried by humans."
(QS. Al-Ahzab: 72)

d. Digital Communication Ethics :

Ethics in communication are highly emphasized in Islam, even in the digital context. Allah SWT states in **Surah Al-Hujurat, verses 11–12**, which emphasize the prohibition against mocking, gossiping, and forming negative assumptions. These values are highly relevant in building a healthy communication culture on social media.

e. Challenges for the Young Muslim Generation in the Digital Era

The younger generation of Muslims faces serious challenges in the form of an identity crisis and moral degradation due to the rapid flow of digital globalization. Some of the emerging phenomena include:

- 1) Digital consumerism and the culture of hedonism.
- 2) Decline in communication ethics on social media.
- 3) Dependence on *gadgets* and non-educational entertainment *content*.
- 4) The spiritual crisis is due to the lack of religious literacy in the use of technology.

Field observations and literature studies indicate that a lack of understanding of Islamic values is a major factor in weakening the moral filter of the younger generation. In this context, the role of families, educational institutions, and digital missionary communities is crucial in instilling Islamic values in a contextual and creative manner.

f. Strategy for Building a Civilized Digital Civilization

To realize a civilized digital civilization based on Islamic values, an integrated strategy is needed across various sectors:

1. Integration of Islamic Values in Digital Education

Education must develop *digital ethics literacy* based on Islamic teachings, so that the younger generation is not only technologically savvy but also ethical in its use. The curriculum needs to combine *digital skills* with *spiritual intelligence*.

2. Creative and Educational Digital Preaching

Muslim preachers and content creators need to present content that is *relatable* to young people's communication styles, while remaining grounded in Quranic and Sunnah values. Da'wah through media such as YouTube, TikTok, and podcasts can be an effective means of spreading Islamic values.

3. The Family as the Center for Internalizing Digital Islamic Values

The family is the first school for digital moral education. Parents need to model media ethics, guide their children in selecting content, and instill the concept of *hisbah* (self-control) from an early age.

4. Strengthening Islamic Digital Communities

Islamic value-based communities online can create positive ecosystems for the younger generation. For example, Islamic digital literacy movements, *creative Muslim communities*, or Quran-based digital ethics campaigns.

g. Implications for the Development of Modern Islamic Civilization

The study's findings demonstrate that Islamic values are highly relevant in shaping a civilized digital civilization. These values are not merely personal moral teachings, but also a social system capable of fostering a just, safe, and dignified digital ecosystem. Thus, building a civilized digital civilization means making Islamic values the moral compass in every digital innovation and interaction. This aligns with Islam's goal as *rahmatan lil 'alamin* (blessing for all the worlds), namely, bringing benefit to all aspects of human life—including the digital sphere.

CLOSING DISCUSSION

A civilized digital civilization can only be realized if the younger generation of Muslims combines technological intelligence with spiritual intelligence. The 5.0 era demands that people not only be *smart users* but also *ethical believers*. Therefore, strengthening Islamic values such as honesty, responsibility, trustworthiness, and good communication must be the foundation of the digital behavior of the current and future generations of Muslims.

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